

Allicin as a potent antibiotic against *E.coli*, *P.vulgaris* & *H.pylori*

Ashish Shrivastava & H. K. Garg*

Department of Biotechnology,
C.S.A. Govt. P. G. Nodal College, Sehore, - 466001 (India)

Department of Zoology & Biotechnology,
Govt. Motilal Vigyan Mahavidyalaya, Bhopal - 462008 (India)

The present study aims at the potential antibacterial value of Allicin against pathogenic bacteria, *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Helicobacter pylori* by disc diffusion method. Bioactive compound Allicin was isolated from the garlic. The results revealed that the Allicin compound are potent in inhibiting these bacteria and this work highlights that the inhibitory effect is on par with standard antibiotics.

Keywords: Allicin, Garlic , Disc Diffusion Method, Inhibitory effect.

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